

THE IMPACT OF ETHNIC VOCAL MUSIC TEACHING ON THE PSYCHOLOGICAL HEALTH OF COLLEGE STUDENTS IN THE CONTEXT OF DISCIPLINARY INTEGRATION

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Abstract

This study examines the relationship between ethnic vocal teaching in universities and the mental health of college students in the context of disciplinary integration. This article elaborates on the various manifestations of disciplinary integration in ethnic singing. Through a questionnaire survey conducted on the aspects of emotional expression, self-awareness, and social interaction, the positive impact of ethnic vocal teaching on the mental health of college students was deeply analyzed. Teaching optimization strategies, such as personalized teaching plan customization, situational teaching and emotional depth experience, cooperative learning and psychological mutual assistance platform construction, stage practice, and psychological growth guidance, are proposed. The purpose of this project is to provide a theoretical basis and practical reference for the organic combination of ethnic vocal teaching and psychological health education in universities and to help college students achieve comprehensive development of psychological health in art learning.

1 Introduction

In today's higher education field, disciplinary integration is an important trend in educational innovation and development. As a key component of art education, ethnic vocal teaching is gradually breaking through the limitations of traditional single disciplines and is actively integrating multiple disciplines. At the same time, the

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mental health of college students is becoming increasingly prominent, representing an important challenge facing higher education. In this context, it is of great theoretical and practical significance to explore the impact of ethnic vocal teaching in universities on the psychological health of college students in the context of disciplinary integration.

2 The presentation of disciplinary integration in the teaching of ethnic vocal music in universities

1) Integration with music technology disciplines

The teaching of ethnic vocal music in universities cannot be separated from the support of music and art disciplines. Music theory knowledge provides a theoretical framework for students to understand the basic elements of melody, rhythm, harmony, and other aspects of ethnic vocal works. For example, when learning a complex ethnic vocal work, students can more accurately grasp the rhythm, melody, and emotional direction of the song by mastering the knowledge of the beat and mode in music theory. Sight singing and ear training can help improve pitch accuracy, rhythm sense, and musical memory, enabling students to quickly and accurately recognize and reproduce music information in ethnic vocal performances. In addition, vocal skills courses, such as vocal techniques and breath control, are closely linked to ethnic vocal teaching, helping students build a scientific and reasonable vocal system, laying a solid foundation for beautiful ethnic singing¹.

(2) Interactions with Psychology

The role of psychology in the teaching of ethnic music in universities is becoming increasingly significant. From the perspective of the teaching process, teachers develop personalized teaching plans based on the principles of educational psychology, students' cognitive characteristics, learning styles, and psychological needs². For example, by understanding students' anxiety when learning new music, teachers can adopt a gradual teaching method to reduce student's psychological pressure. In relation to vocal performance, performance psychology provides theoretical guidance and practical methods for students to overcome stage fear. Through psychological adjustment training, such as relaxation exercises and positive self-suggestions, students can better control their emotions on stage and demonstrate stable and excellent singing skills.

(3) Interweaving cultural studies

Ethnic vocal music is a treasure of ethnic culture, with intricate connections to cultural studies. China numerous ethnic vocal works contain rich cultural connotations, including elements of ethnic history, folk customs, religious beliefs, and more. In teaching, teachers guide students to delve deeper into the cultural stories behind their works, such as by introducing them to Mongolian nomadic culture, grassland life, and their reverence for nature. The integration of cultural studies and ethnic vocal teaching not only enriches students' cultural knowledge reserves and enhances their sense of national identity and cultural confidence in cultural inheritance and exchange, laying a solid spiritual foundation for their mental health development.

3、 Design and Implementation of Questionnaire Survey

(1) Questionnaire design

To gain a deeper understanding of the impact of ethnic vocal music teaching in universities on the mental health of college students, this study designed a questionnaire. The questionnaire includes basic information about the students, their experience learning ethnic vocal music, changes in their psychological state before and after learning (such as emotional stability, self-confidence, social skills, etc.), and their understanding of the

relationship between ethnic vocal music teaching and mental health.

(2) Survey subjects and implementation

We selected students majoring in ethnic vocal music from universities and non-professional students who took ethnic vocal courses as survey subjects. A total of 200 questionnaires were distributed, and 192 valid questionnaires were collected, with an effective response rate of 96%.

4 Survey Results and Analysis

(1) The emotional aspect

Data shows that over 86% of students reported an improvement in their emotional regulation ability after learning ethnic vocal music. Among them, 68% of students believed that they could better cope with the pressure of learning and life and alleviate negative emotions by singing ethnic vocal works when feeling down. For example, when facing exam pressure, many students choose to sing soothing ethnic songs to relax and effectively relieve their tense emotions.

(2) Examine self-awareness

According to the survey, approximately 91% of students reported that learning ethnic vocal music has a positive impact on their self-awareness. During the learning process, through continuous singing practice and feedback from teachers and classmates, students gained a clearer understanding of their vocal skills and artistic expression. 86% of students also expressed increased confidence and were more willing to actively showcase their talents in campus cultural activities and other occasions.

(3) Assessing social skills

In the social competence survey, 96% of students reported that activities such as choir singing and group performances in ethnic vocal courses promoted communication and cooperation between them and their classmates. Among them, 78% of students reported that their communication and coordination skills had significantly improved in team collaboration, and they were more willing to participate in social activities such as school clubs and cultural performances and made more like-minded friends.

5 The positive impact of ethnic vocal music teaching on the mental health of college students in China

(1) Emotional catharsis and emotional regulation

Ethnic vocal works have a strong emotional carrying capacity, covering various levels of human emotions. During the process of learning and singing ethnic vocal works, college students are able to integrate their own emotions with those in the works and achieve emotional release and regulation. For example, when students sing a piece that expresses sad emotions, they can integrate their negative emotions such as setbacks and losses encountered in life into the song and release their inner pressure through artistic expression. At the same time, singing cheerful and cheerful works can also evoke positive emotional experiences in students, enabling them to break free from negative emotions and achieve psychological balance and harmony.

(2) Improvement of esthetic literacy and psychological pleasure

Teaching ethnic vocal music in universities is an important carrier of esthetic education³. Ethnic vocal works integrate beautiful melodies, moving lyrics, unique singing styles, and rich cultural connotations, providing college students with a comprehensive esthetic experience. When appreciating and singing ethnic vocal works, students' esthetic perception, esthetic imagination, esthetic understanding, and esthetic creation abilities are

exercised and enhanced. The improvement of esthetic literacy is accompanied by the generation of psychological pleasure, because esthetic experience can stimulate the secretion of neurotransmitters such as endorphins in the brain, causing people to experience pleasant and satisfying emotions, effectively alleviating the tension and anxiety faced by college students in their studies and life and promoting mental health.

(3) Enhancing self-awareness and confidence

Learning ethnic vocal music is a process of constantly challenging oneself and surpassing oneself. In this process, college students can gain a deeper understanding of their abilities, potential, and shortcomings through mastering vocal techniques, expressing emotions in their works, and practicing stage performances. When students make progress in learning ethnic vocal music, such as successfully singing a difficult piece, achieving excellent results in competitions, or receiving recognition from teachers and classmates, they will gain a strong sense of achievement and confidence. The establishment of this confidence can be transferred to other aspects of college students lives, enabling them to face various challenges, such as learning, socializing, and career planning, with a more positive and optimistic attitude, thereby promoting the overall improvement of their mental health level.

(4) Social interaction and promotion of interpersonal relationships

The forms of choir singing, group performances, and vocal club activities in ethnic singing in universities provide rich social interaction opportunities for college students. In these activities, students must work closely and collaborate with others to create and perform musical works together. In the process of cooperation, students learn to listen to others' opinions, respect their personalities, and coordinate their differences, thereby improving their interpersonal communication skills and establishing good interpersonal relationships. Good interpersonal relationships are important for the mental health of college students. They can provide emotional support, a sense of belonging, and security, reduce the occurrence of negative emotions, such as loneliness and depression, and promote healthy mental health.

6 Optimization strategies for ethnic vocal teaching in universities to promote students mental health

(1) Personalized teaching plan customization

Fully consider the individual differences in college students, including their psychological characteristics, music foundation, interests, and hobbies, and develop personalized ethnic vocal teaching plans. For students who are introverted and have difficulty expressing their emotions, they can choose ethnic vocal works with delicate emotions and strong expressive power and use one-on-one tutoring, group sharing, and other teaching methods to encourage them to open up and boldly express their emotions. For students with weak music foundation but high learning enthusiasm, progressive teaching content, from basic vocal training to simple performance of works, should be designed to gradually establish their learning confidence and sense of achievement to meet the psychological needs of different students and promote their mental health development.

(2) Situational teaching and deep emotional experiences

Create diverse teaching scenarios to enhance the emotional experience of college students learning ethnic vocal music. Teachers can use multimedia technology to play background videos of ethnic vocal works and documentaries on ethnic customs, etc., allowing students to intuitively experience the cultural atmosphere and emotional background contained in the works. For example, when teaching a national vocal work with strong regional characteristics, displaying local natural scenery, folk activities and other visual materials can make

students feel as if they are in the context depicted in the work. At the same time, organize students to participate in role-playing, scenario simulation, and other activities, allowing them to sing works in specific contexts, further deepening emotional experiences, improving the authenticity and infectiousness of emotional expression, and promoting the healthy development of student's emotions.

(3) Building a collaborative learning and psychological mutual aid platform

Vigorously conduct cooperative learning activities for ethnic vocal music and build a psychological mutual-aid platform for students. In classroom teaching, students should form vocal learning groups to jointly complete rehearsal and performance tasks. Encourage members within the group to communicate, evaluate, help each other, and share their learning and singing experiences. In the process of group cooperation, students can not only improve their vocal performance skills, but also enhance their psychological resilience through mutual support and encouragement, cultivate teamwork spirit, and sense of collective honor. In addition, they should establish vocal learning communities or online communication platforms to facilitate students' communication and interaction in their spare time, expand their social circle, provide more psychological support resources for students, and promote the improvement of their mental health.

(4) Stage practice and psychological growth guidance

Increase opportunities for college students to practice ethnic vocal music on stage and strengthen psychological growth guidance during the stage practice process. Schools and teachers should actively organize various vocal performances, competitions, presentations, and other activities to allow students to exercise their singing abilities and psychological qualities on stage. Before the stage practice, provide students with systematic psychological counseling, including relaxation training, concentration training, and development of psychological contingency plans for unexpected situations. After the stage practice, organize students to reflect and summarize their psychology, guide them to correctly view the success and failure of stage performance, draw nutrients for psychological growth from practical experience, continuously improve their psychological adjustment ability and ability to cope with pressure, and enable students to achieve comprehensive psychological health development in stage practice.

7 Conclusion

In summary, teaching ethnic vocal music in universities under the context of disciplinary integration has multiple positive impacts on the mental health of college students. Through the integration of multiple disciplines such as music and art, psychology, etc., ethnic vocal teaching provides strong support and guarantees for the psychological health development of college students in terms of emotional expression and regulation, esthetic literacy improvement, self-awareness and confidence enhancement, social interaction, and interpersonal relationship promotion. To better leverage this positive impact, ethnic vocal education workers in universities should actively explore and implement teaching optimization strategies based on promoting mental health, organically combining ethnic vocal education with college students' mental health education, and contributing to the cultivation of high-quality talent with physical and mental health and comprehensive development.

Reference:

¹Wang Cizhao Music Esthetics [M] Higher Education Press, 2004

²Zhang Dajun, Educational Psychology [M], People's Education Press, 2015

³Tian Qing, A Brief History of Chinese Music [M]. Shanghai Music Publishing House, 2001

Annex 1

Questionnaire on the Impact of Ethnic Vocal Music Teaching in Colleges and Universities on the Psychological Health of Students with Discipline Integration

Dear students,

Hello! To gain a deeper understanding of the impact of ethnic vocal music teaching in universities on the mental health of college students, we conducted a questionnaire survey. Your answer will provide an important reference for our research. The questionnaire will be anonymous and will take approximately 10-15 minutes to complete. Please feel free to fill in according to the actual situation. Thank you for your support and cooperation.

Part 1: Personal Information

1. Your gender:

A. Male B. Female

2. Your grade level:

A. First year B. Second year C. Third year D. Fourth year

3. The major you are studying:

A. Ethnic Vocal Music Majors

B. Other music majors (such as Western vocal music, instrumental music, etc.)

C. Music major (please specify:)

4. Time spent learning ethnic vocal music:

A. 1 year

B. 1-2 years

C. 2-3 years

D. More than 3 years

Part Two: Experience of learning ethnic vocal music

1. What is your original intention in learning ethnic vocal music? (Multiple Choice)

A. Personal interests and hobbies

B. School curriculum arrangement

C. Enhance artistic cultivation

D. Influenced by others (such as family members, friends, idols)

E. Other (please specify:)

2. The approximate amount of time you spend participating in ethnic vocal learning or practice per week is as follows:

A. 1-3 hours

B. 3-5 hours

C. 5-7 hours

D. More than 7 hours

3. What are the main ways in which you learn ethnic vocal music? (Multiple Choice)

- A. School curriculum teaching
- B. Participate in extracurricular vocal coaching classes
- C. Personal self-study (such as watching instructional videos, reading books, etc.)
- D. Joining a vocal club or choir
- E. Other (please specify:)

Part 3: The emotional aspect

1. Before learning ethnic vocal music, your overall emotional state is as follows:

- A. Very stable with few emotional fluctuations
- B. Relatively stable, occasionally experiencing emotional fluctuations
- C. Emotionally unstable and easily influenced by external factors
- D. Emotionally unstable, often in a state of anxiety, depression, or other negative emotions

2. After learning ethnic vocal music, do you feel that your emotional regulation ability has changed?

- A. Significant improvement, allowing effective control of emotions
- B. There is a certain improvement that can be alleviated through singing and other methods when the mood is not good.
- C. There is no significant changes
- D. I feel like my emotional regulation ability has actually declined.

3. When you encounter stress or difficulties, do you use singing ethnic vocals to soothe your emotions?

- A. Always, this is one of my main ways of reducing stress.
- B. It often feels somewhat helpful
- C. Occasionally, depending on the situation
- D. Almost not

4. Which situation do you think can generate the most positive emotions in the process of learning ethnic vocal music? (Multiple Choice)

- A. Mastering a new song
- B. Received praise and affirmation from the teacher
- C. Success in performances and competitions
- D. Interactions with classmates during choir or rehearsal
- E. Other (please specify:)

Part 4: Self-awareness

1. How confident were you before learning the ethnic vocal music?

- A. Very confident, believing that I can do well in all aspects
- B. More confident, with a certain level of self-confidence
- C. Not very confident, having doubts about one's own abilities
- D. Very unconfident, always feeling inferior to others

2. Has your self-awareness of your image and abilities changed after learning ethnic vocal music?

- A. There has been a significant change, and I feel more charming and capable now.
- B. There have been some changes, and I have become more confident in certain aspects.
- C. unchanged
- D. I'm not quite sure.

3. Have you become more aware of your strengths and weaknesses as you learn ethnic vocal music?

- A. Yes, very clear and able to make targeted improvements
- B. I am quite clear about some of my strengths and weaknesses.

C. I'm not quite sure. I haven't thought deeply about it.

D. I am completely unsure.

4. Do you think that learning ethnic vocal music impacts your values and attitude toward life?

A. It has had a great impact, providing me with a new understanding and pursuit of life.

B. It had a certain impact and changed my thinking in certain aspects.

C. The impact is not significant

D. No impact

Part Five: Social Skills

1. Before learning ethnic vocal music, your social circle mainly consisted of the following:

A. Extensive, with many friends and social activities

B. Relatively broad, with some fixed friends and social circles.

C. Relatively narrow, mainly for classmates and family members.

D. Very narrow, with almost no social activities

2. Have you made more friends after learning about ethnic vocal music?

A. Yes, I have made many interesting friends.

B. There are some classmates or partners in the vocal learning process.

C. There is no significant changes

D. On the contrary, due to my focus on learning vocal music, I have fewer friends.

3. How did you collaborate with your classmates in activities such as choir singing and group performances in ethnic vocal courses?

A. Very good, able to communicate and collaborate effectively

B. Good: occasionally, there may be some minor friction, but it does not affect the overall cooperation.

C. Generally, there are difficulties during the cooperation process.

D. Not good, conflicts, and problems often arise

4. Do you think that learning ethnic vocal music impacts your enthusiasm for participating in other social activities, such as club activities and gatherings?

A. There has been a significant improvement, and I am more willing to actively participate in various social activities.

B. I have made progress and will try to participate in social activities related to vocal music.

C. There is no significant changes

D. On the contrary, it reduces enthusiasm for participating in social activities.

Part Six: Cognition of the Relationship between Ethnic Vocal Music Teaching and Mental Health

1. Do you think that teaching ethnic music has a positive impact on the mental health of college students?

A. I strongly agree and feel that the impact is significant.

B. I agree and have a certain positive impact.

C. I'm not quite sure. There's no obvious feeling.

D. I disagree and feel that there is no relationship between the two.

2. Would you like teachers to pay more attention to student's mental health in ethnic singing lessons?

A. I believe that relevant teaching content and activities should be included.

B. I hope that psychological health education can be appropriately integrated into the teaching process.

C. It doesn't matter, follow the teacher's arrangement.

D. I don't want it. I think it will affect the teaching of vocal music majors.

3. What ways do you think ethnic singing can better promote the mental health of college students? (Multiple Choice)

A. Integrating psychological counseling courses and lectures with ethnic singing instruction

- B. Teachers must pay attention to student's emotional changes and psychological needs during the teaching process.
- C. Organize more vocal performance activities related to mental health, such as themed concerts
- D. Provide more opportunities for teamwork and communication and cultivate students' social skills
- E. Other (please specify:)

Thank you again for taking the time to fill out the questionnaire.